

Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI)

Glycine functionalized silica is an effective adsorbent for cobalt(II) and nickel(II) recovery

Jędrzej Piątek,^a Caspar N. de Bruin-Dickason,^a Aleksander Jaworski,^a Tetyana Budnyak^{a,*} and Adam Slabon^{a,*}

^a *Department of Materials and Environmental Chemistry, Stockholm University, 106 91 Stockholm.*

* *Corresponding authors e-mails: adam.slabon@mmk.su.se, tetyana.budnyak@mmk.su.se*

Contents

- 1. Supplemental figures**
- 2. Tables**

1. Supplemental figures

Fig. S1. Comparison of thermogravimetric analysis for SiO₂ (red trace), SiO₂-NH₂ (black trace) and SiO₂-Gly (blue trace).

Fig. S2. Thermogravimetric analysis for SiO₂.

Fig. S3. Thermogravimetric analysis for SiO₂-NH₂.

Fig. S4. Thermogravimetric analysis for SiO₂-Gly + Co(II).

Fig. S5. Thermogravimetric analysis for SiO₂-Gly + Ni(II).

Fig. S6. BJH curve of pore-size distribution by area for SiO₂-Gly material.

Fig. S7. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms for SiO_2 .

Fig. S8. BJH curve of pore size distribution by volume for SiO_2 .

Fig. S9. BJH curve of pore size distribution by area for SiO₂.

Fig. S10. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms for SiO₂-NH₂.

Fig. S11. BJH curve of pore size distribution by volume for SiO₂-NH₂.

Fig. S12. BJH curve of pore size distribution by area for SiO₂-NH₂.

Fig. S13. SEM micrograph of SiO₂.

Fig. S14. SEM micrograph of SiO₂-Gly.

Fig. S15. Effect of initial pH on adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II) on SiO₂-Gly material.

Fig. S16. Co(II) adsorption using NH₄OH and Na₂CO₃ solutions for initial pH adjustment.

Fig. S17. Kinetics of Co(II) and Ni(II) adsorption on SiO₂-Gly material.

Fig. S18. Pseudo-first order plot for adsorption of Co(II) and Ni(II) on SiO₂-Gly.

Fig. S19. Langmuir isotherm model chart for Co(II) adsorption.

Fig. S20. Freundlich isotherm model chart for Co(II) adsorption.

Fig. S21. Temkin isotherm model chart for Co(II) adsorption.

Fig. S22. Langmuir isotherm model chart for Ni(II) adsorption.

Fig. S23. Freundlich isotherm model chart for Ni(II) adsorption.

Fig. S24. Temkin isotherm model chart for Ni(II) adsorption.

Fig. S25. FTIR spectra of SiO₂-Gly material before (black trace) and after adsorption of Co(II) (red trace) and Ni(II) (purple trace) ions.

2. Tables

Table S1. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption data for SiO₂ and SiO₂-NH₂.

Parameter	SiO ₂	SiO ₂ -NH ₂
BET surface area (m ² ·g ⁻¹)	428.6	322.9
BJH adsorption average pore size diameter (nm)	5.4	5.8
BJH desorption average pore size diameter (nm)	4.9	5.1